

High Intensity Radiated Field External Environments for Civil Aircraft

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Abstract: NAWCAD Patuxent River, Maryland, was tasked by the FAA to determine the High Intensity Radiated Field (HIRF) levels for civil aircraft operating in the U.S. The electromagnetic field survey apply to civil aircraft seeking FAA certification under Federal Aviation Regulations. The HIRF survey determined the Rotorcraft Severe, Fixed Wing Severe, Certification, and Normal Environments that civil aircraft may be exposed to while operating in the continental U.S. and its territories. The HIRF survey was accomplished by accessing EME data bases, technical manuals, and phone contact with emitter operators to determine the HIRF drivers, analyze the severity, and provide a U.S. composite environment. The US HIRF environments were subsequently harmonization with the European HIRF environment into what is known as the International HIRF environments.

INTRODUCTION

On 10 February 1988 [1], the Society of Automotive Engineering (SAE) was requested to develop guidance for designers aircraft, aircraft engine, and electronics components on how to maximize protection of airborne avionics and electronic systems from the adverse effects of high energy RF fields through which aircraft may fly. The SAE created under the AE4 EMC Committee the AE4R Radiated Environments Subcommittee. The AE4R was organized into three panels. Panel 1 was set up to analyze and validate the HIRF environment that the FAA had developed. Panel 2 was set up to write the high level advisory material that would support the FAA's HIRF rule making efforts. Panel 3 was set up to write an SAE Aerospace Recommend Practices (ARP) document that provided design and certification methods, later known as the HIRF User's Guide/Manual.

Concurrently with the FAA efforts, the JAA in Europe had gone to the European Organization for Civil Aviation Equipment (EUROCAE) with a similar request. EUROCAE set up a similar organization under a group called Working Group 33, HIRF. In an early effort to get international agreement on the technical efforts, the EUROCAE members participated in numerous AER4 meetings held in the U.S.

The FAA had contracted the DOD Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Center (ECAC) in 1987 to research and define the U.S. high energy RF field environmental envelope to be used for type certification of aircraft and aircraft engines and for the technical standards orders (TSO) authorization of electronic equipment. Panel 1 reviewed the environment data, methods for calculating field strength, and assumptions. The SAE AE4R Panel 1 effort ended with the freezing of the Part 25 Severe Certification and Normal Environments and their corresponding assumptions. The frozen HIRF environments and assumptions were incorporated into a final draft of the advisory circular in 1992. At this point in time, the FAA and JAA had decided that the HIRF rule needed further international harmonization before it could be used in the FAA rule making process. The FAA tasked the Aviation Rulemaking Advisory Committee (ARAC), at the end of 1992, to harmonize the rule and make the necessary adjustment to the supporting documents.

The only activity that was on going after this point in the SAE AE4R Panel 1 was a small subpanel that was trying to define the rotorcraft

environment. The SAE AE4R Panel 1 Rotorcraft Subpanel and their corresponding group in EUROCAE WG-33 continued to work together to define the assumptions, review emitter data, and propose HIRF environments for rotorcraft. These groups worked closely with the ARAC group to provide a harmonized environment that was completed in June 1997.

The EEHWG was established in 1993 by the ARAC Transport Airplane and Engine Subcommittee (TAES) in response to the public announcement by the FAA in the Federal Register, Vol. 57, No. 239, December 1992. The EEHWG was chartered with making recommendation to the TAES concerning the FAA disposition of the HIRF and Lightning requirements. The EEHWG took the reports prepared by SAE and EUROCAE and converted them into a harmonized Advisory Circular/Advisory Material Joint (AC/AMJ 20.1317) and User's Manual/User's Guide. The EEHWG also took the FAA Notice of Proposed Rule Making (NPRM) and the Joint Aviation Authority (JAA) Notice of Proposed Amendment (NPA) HIRF materials and converted them into a harmonized NPRM/NPA document.

The EEHWG need to create harmonized NPRN/NPA documents for each part of the FAR, drove a need for expanding the scope of the HIRF environments from just Part 25 to Parts 23, 25, 27, and 29. The FAA had tasked NAWCAD in 1994 [2] to conduct this HIRF Electromagnetic Field Survey study which complemented the efforts of the EEHWG and the SAE AE4R Rotorcraft Subcommittee. The frozen environment needed to be updated to include Part 23 commuter and general aviation airplanes and Parts 27 and 29 for rotorcraft. The assumptions for the various types of fixed wing aircraft and rotorcraft had to be adjusted for the inclusion of VFR's and the corresponding flight envelope of the aircraft (i.e., hovering and vertical landing/takeoff).

The International HIRF environment ended up with following environments:

- Rotorcraft Severe Environment.
- Fixed Wing Aircraft Severe HIRF Environment.
- Aircraft Certification HIRF Environment.
- Aircraft Normal HIRF Environment.

These HIRF environments and assumptions were incorporated into the joint NPRN/NPA and AC/AMJ material and distributed at the November 1997 meeting of EEHWG.

Early in the efforts of the SAE, there were requests for flight validation of some of the levels being predicted. To this end several studies to investigate the phenomena and document the exposure seen were conducted.

The FAA Technical Center in 1988 contracted Ohio University Avionics Engineering Center to provide test measurements flights (in DC-3 aircraft equipped with RF field strength measurement equipment) of the field strength to be encountered at four sites: 1) 100 kHz: Loran-C, Carolina Beach, North Carolina; 2) 15.195 and 11.939 MHz: Voice of America, HF Broadcast, Greenville, North Carolina; 3) 21.5 MHz: Over-the-Horizon Radar (OTH-B), Moscow, Maine; 4) 3 GHz: TPS-75 Radar, Baltimore, Maryland [3].

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Table 1
NPRN/NPA ASSUMPTIONS SUMMARY

Source	Rotorcraft Severe	Fixed Wing Severe	All Aircraft Certification	All Aircraft Normal
	Distance (ft)	Distance (ft)	Distance (ft)	Distance (ft)
Airport/Heliport/Off Shore Platforms				
Fixed:				
Air route/Airport surveillance radar	300 slant	500 slant	500 slant	500 slant
All other	100 direct	250 slant < 5 miles	250 slant < 5 miles	250 slant < 5 miles
Mobile:				
Aircraft's weather radar	150 direct	150 direct	150 direct	250 direct
All others	50 direct	50 direct	50 direct	50 direct
Non-Airport/Heliport/Off Shore Platforms				
HIRF Special Use Airspace (SUA's)	Edge of SUA	Edge of SUA	Edge of SUA	Edge of SUA
All others (radial from facility)				
>0-3 nmi	100 direct	500 slant	500 slant	500 slant
3-5 nmi	100 direct	500 slant	1000 slant	1000 slant
5-10 nmi	100 direct	500 slant	1000 slant	1500 slant
10-25 nmi	100 direct	500 slant	1000 slant	2500 slant
>25 nmi	100 direct	500 slant	1000 slant	1000 slant
Ship-Based Transmitters				
All Ships	500 direct	500 slant	1000 slant	not applicable
Air to Air				
Interceptor	not applicable	500 direct	500 direct	not applicable
All others	not applicable	100 direct	100 direct	not applicable

NASA, under the fly-by-light, powered-by-wire program, flew a 757 near several sites to compare modeling and flight test results. Descriptions of the flight test efforts are provided in references [4, 5 and 6].

The FAA Technical Center arranged to conduct several flight tests with their S-76 helicopter to evaluate the practicality of performing aircraft level HIRF tests, determine the effects of HIRF on a specific rotorcraft with the potential to obtain information on rotorcraft in general, and evaluate the effects of exposure to "real world" HIRF emitters. The results of the flight tests are detailed in references [7, 8, and 9].

It was concluded from the study that HIRF levels do exist and modeling techniques should continue to be used to estimate the HIRF levels.

ASSUMPTIONS

The assumptions from the NPRN/NPA and AC/AMJ are summarized in the table 1

ANALYSIS METHODS

The methodology used to collect and reduce the data for the US HIRF environment is shown in figure 1. This process was iterated for the assumptions for Rotorcraft Severe, Fixed Wing Severe, Certification, and Normal HIRF Environments. The peak and average field strengths were tabulated and graphed for presentation.

The analysis of the electromagnetic field produce by an emitter was done using classical antenna propagation theory. In the near-field region, the gain is a function of the linear distance from the antenna and aperture type; consequently, the antenna performance must be evaluated using special considerations.

The power densities in the near field are calculated using the far field and a near-field gain reduction factor χ as shown in equation 1.

All emitter antennas were classified as having one of the following apertures: a rectangular aperture, circular aperture, or a linear aperture. Phase array antennas are treated as rectangular or circular apertures. Elliptical or crossed polarized antennas are treated as either

Figure 1
US HIRF EME Development Process

$$P_D = \frac{P_T G \chi}{4\pi r^2} \tag{1}$$

Where:
 P_D = Power Density (watts/meter²)
 P_T = Transmitter Output Power (watts)
 G = Antenna Gain (unitless)
 χ = Near-Field Gain Reduction Factor (unitless)
 r = Distance or Range from Antenna (meters)
 π = The Constant Pi (3.1415...)

circular or rectangular antennas depending upon the ratio of the elliptical wave.

The methods presented in the following section of this paper for calculating near-field gain reduction factors were initially proposed by Alexander Gross of Joint Spectrum Center. SAE AE4R and EUROCAE extensively reviewed, validated, and adopted these methods as the way near-field reduction would be estimated. These unique near-field models became known within the HIRF community as the "Gross" method.

Linear Aperture. A linear aperture has maximum overall dimensions, which is not large compared to the wavelength. Therefore, no near field correction is used. Typical antennas that meet this requirement are dipoles and monopoles.

Rectangular Apertures Rectangular apertures are horns or partial dish antennas (so-called orange peel antennas). A rectangular aperture antenna may not have the same vertical and horizontal axis illumination taper. Therefore, the gain reduction for each axis is independently determined. The near-field reduction for either axis is shown in figure 2.

FIGURE 2
NEAR-FIELD CORRECTION FACTORS FOR
RECTANGULAR APERTURE

Next, the distance from the antenna must be normalized by dividing by the far-field boundary for each axis. The normalized distance for each axis is determined using equation 2 for the horizontal axis and equation 3 for the vertical axis.

$$\Delta_h = \frac{r f}{d_h^2 300} \quad \Delta_v = \frac{r f}{d_v^2 300} \quad (2) \text{ and } (3)$$

Where:
 Δ_h = Horizontal Axis Normalized Distance (unitless)
 r = Separation Distance or range (meters)
 f = Transmitter Carrier Frequency (MHz)
 d_h = Horizontal Axis Dimension (meters)
 Δ_v = Vertical Axis Normalized Distance (unitless)
 d_v = Vertical Axis Dimension (meters)

From figure 2, find the near-field gain reduction factors (either χ_h or χ_v) using the axis illuminations and the normalized distances from equations 2 and 3 (Δ_h and Δ_v). The total near-field gain reduction is the sum of the gain reduction in dB converted to a numeric factor as given in equation 4.

$$\chi = 10^{-((\chi_h + \chi_v)/10)} \quad (4)$$

Where:
 χ = Total Near-Field Reduction Factor (unitless)
 χ_h = Horizontal Near-Field Reduction Factor (dB)
 χ_v = Vertical Near-Field Reduction Factor (dB)

The total near-field reduction factor (χ) is used in equation 1 to obtain the power density.

Circular Aperture Circular apertures refer to transmission line to space wave couplers that are truly a circle in shape. Examples of such aperture are parabolic dish, circular planar array, log spirals, and circular horns. The near-field reduction for either axis is shown in figure 3.

To calculate the near-field power density, equation 1 is used, where the value "r" is set at the far-field boundary and the circular's near-field reduction factor (χ_c) as determined above. The resulting equation is shown in equation 5.

FIGURE 3
NEAR-FIELD CORRECTION FACTORS FOR CIRCULAR
APERTURES

$$P_D = \frac{300^2 P_t G \chi_c}{16 \pi d_c^4 f} \quad (5)$$

Where:
 P_D = Power Density (watts/meter²)
 P_t = Transmitter Output Power (watts)
 G = Antenna Gain (unitless)
 χ_c = Near-Field Gain Reduction Factor (unitless)
 d_c = Circular Aperture Diameter (meters)
 π = The Constant Pi (3.141592...)
 f = Frequency of Transmitter (MHz)

Average and Peak Power. For systems using AM, FM, or PCM modulations, the peak power was set at the transmitters CW output rating, and average power was set equal to peak power. In radar application, the equipment modulation characteristics are used. Peak and average transmitter power outputs are related as shown in equation 6.

$$P_{Ta} = P_{Tp} D \quad (6)$$

Where:
 D = Duty Cycle (unitless, duty/100)
 P_{Tp} = Transmitter Peak Output (watts)
 P_{Ta} = Transmitter Average Output (watts)

Direct Illumination. Direct illumination of an emitter occurs when an aircraft can be in the main beam of the antenna. Rotorcraft were almost always possible of being illuminated by the main beam of the antenna because the separation distance from the emitter was a bubble of a 100 ft radius from the ground up and around the emitter. Fixed wing aircraft would encounter this situation when the emitter has no restriction where it could radiate its main beam of energy.

Slant Illumination. The slant illumination is the result of an emitter having a maximum elevation angle that the main beam of the antenna can be raised to. The fixed wing aircraft are limited to minimum emitter ground separations of 500 ft and higher. This situation is illustrated in figure 4 with an example emitter limited to 30 degrees elevation.

FIGURE 4
ILLUSTRATION OF SLANT ILLUMINATION

Overhead Illuminations. Another aspect of elevation limited antennas is the possibility of a higher overhead power density than experienced at the slant range. Figure 5 illustrates an exaggerated version of this situation.

FIGURE 5
ILLUSTRATION OF OVERHEAD ILLUMINATION

If the side lobe level was known for an emitter, it was used. The default value if unknown was set to 15 dB below the main lobe.

Power Density to Field Strength. Each of the power densities (peak, average, overhead, etc.) were converted to equivalent field strength values using the impedance of free space air as shown in equation 7. The resulting electric field intensities were used to find the highest driver emitter for peak field intensity and the highest emitter driver for the average field intensity for each of the 17 bands.

$$E = (P_d Z)^{(1/2)} \quad (7)$$

Where:

- E = Electric Field Intensity (volts/meter)
- P_d = Power Density (watts/meter)
- Z = Impedance of free space air (120π or 377 ohms)

The International HIRF Environment was developed at the EEHWG meeting at Bridgeport in June 1997 using the U.S. and European HIRF environment data. The International HIRF Environment is a harmonized version of these environments with tailoring consideration as follows:

- The level maintained some relationship to 1997 and prior HIRF special conditions environments.
- Consolidation of frequency bands.
- High confidence that aircraft will not be affected by HIRF.
- Environments below 400 MHz were rounded to 50 or 100 V/m (this is where most EMI effects are observed in

aircraft; therefore, high confidence is gained that the aircraft is protected).

- Environments above 1 GHz were rounded to the nearest 100 V/m with a maximum of 3,000 V/m or nearest 100 V/m average.
- Considered a test environment so it should not have to change every time a transmitter changes.
- Practicality of design and test levels.

CONCLUSIONS

The International HIRF Environments are provided as follows:

- Rotorcraft Severe: table 2 and graphed in figures 6 and 7.
- Fixed Wing: table 3 and graphed in 8 and 9
- Certification table 4 and graphed in figures 10 and 11
- Normal table 5 and graphed in figures 12 and 13

For more details regarding the topic of this paper refer to reference [10].

TABLE 2
ROTORCRAFT SEVERE ENVIRONMENT DATA

Range	Peak	Driver	Average	Driver
10 kHz to 100 kHz	150	European	150	European
100 kHz to 500 kHz	200	U.S.	200	European
500 kHz to 2 MHz	200	European	200	European
2 MHz to 30 MHz	200	European	200	European
30 MHz to 70 MHz	200	European	200	European
70 MHz to 100 MHz	200	European	200	European
100 MHz to 200 MHz	200	European	200	U.S.
200 MHz to 400 MHz	200	European	200	U.S.
400 MHz to 700 MHz	730	European	200	European
700 MHz to 1 GHz	1,400	European	240	U.S.
1 GHz to 2 GHz	5,000	U.S.	250	European
2 GHz to 4 GHz	6,000	European	490	European
4 GHz to 6 GHz	7,200	European	400	European
6 GHz to 8 GHz	1,100	European	170	European
8 GHz to 12 GHz	5,000	European	330	European
12 GHz to 18 GHz	2,000	European	330	European
18 GHz to 40 GHz	1,000	European	420	European

FIGURE 6
PEAK ROTORCRAFT SEVERE ENVIRONMENT

**FIGURE 7
AVERAGE ROTORCRAFT SEVERE ENVIRONMENT**

**TABLE 3
FIXED WING SEVERE ENVIRONMENT DATA**

Range	Peak	Driver	Average	Driver
10 kHz to 100 kHz	50	European	50	European
100 kHz to 500 kHz	60	European	60	European
500 kHz to 2 MHz	70	European	70	European
2 MHz to 30 MHz	200	European	200	European
30 MHz to 70 MHz	30	European	30	European
70 MHz to 100 MHz	30	European	30	European
100 MHz to 200 MHz	90	European	30	European
200 MHz to 400 MHz	70	European	70	European
400 MHz to 700 MHz	730	European	80	U.S.
700 MHz to 1 GHz	1,400	European	240	U.S.
1 GHz to 2 GHz	3,300	European	160	European
2 GHz to 4 GHz	4,500	European	490	European
4 GHz to 6 GHz	7,200	U.S.	300	U.S.
6 GHz to 8 GHz	1,100	European	170	European
8 GHz to 12 GHz	2,600	European	330	European
12 GHz to 18 GHz	2,000	European	330	European
18 GHz to 40 GHz	1,000	European	420	European

**FIGURE 9
AVERAGE FIXED WING SEVERE ENVIRONMENT**

**TABLE 4
CERTIFICATION ENVIRONMENT DATA**

Range	Peak	Driver	Average	Driver
10 kHz to 100 kHz	50	European	50	European
100 kHz to 500 kHz	50	European	50	European
500 kHz to 2 MHz	50	European	50	European
2 MHz to 30 MHz	100	U.S.	100	U.S.
30 MHz to 70 MHz	50	European	50	European
70 MHz to 100 MHz	50	European	50	European
100 MHz to 200 MHz	100	European	100	European
200 MHz to 400 MHz	100	European	100	European
400 MHz to 700 MHz	700	European	50	U.S.
700 MHz to 1 GHz	700	European	100	European
1 GHz to 2 GHz	2,000	European	200	European
2 GHz to 4 GHz	3,000	European	200	European
4 GHz to 6 GHz	3,000	U.S.	200	U.S.
6 GHz to 8 GHz	1,000	European	200	European
8 GHz to 12 GHz	3,000	European	300	European
12 GHz to 18 GHz	2,000	European	200	European
18 GHz to 40 GHz	600	European	200	European

**FIGURE 8
PEAK FIXED WING SEVERE ENVIRONMENT**

**FIGURE 10
PEAK CERTIFICATION ENVIRONMENT**

FIGURE 11
AVERAGE CERTIFICATION ENVIRONMENT

FIGURE 13
AVERAGE NORMAL ENVIRONMENT

TABLE 5
NORMAL ENVIRONMENT DATA

Range	Peak	Driver	Average	Driver
10 kHz to 100 kHz	20	European	20	European
100 kHz to 500 kHz	20	European	20	European
500 kHz to 2 MHz	30	European	30	European
2 MHz to 30 MHz	100	U.S.	100	U.S.
30 MHz to 70 MHz	10	European	10	European
70 MHz to 100 MHz	10	European	10	European
100 MHz to 200 MHz	30	European	10	U.S.
200 MHz to 400 MHz	10	U.S.	10	U.S.
400 MHz to 700 MHz	700	European	40	U.S.
700 MHz to 1 GHz	700	European	40	U.S.
1 GHz to 2 GHz	1,300	European	160	European
2 GHz to 4 GHz	3,000	European	120	European
4 GHz to 6 GHz	3,000	U.S.	160	U.S.
6 GHz to 8 GHz	400	European	170	European
8 GHz to 12 GHz	1,230	U.S.	230	European
12 GHz to 18 GHz	730	European	190	U.S.
18 GHz to 40 GHz	600	European	150	European

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FIGURE 12
PEAK NORMAL ENVIRONMENT